

Plight of Migrant Labours in Thiruvananthapuram District of Kerala

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Introduction

Inbound migration is more relevant in the scenario of India. India, the growing economy witnessing the gap between haves and have nots are alarming. Unemployment and migration are closely interconnected. The rate of unemployment and gulf boom (after 1970) accelerated the youth migration from Kerala to Gulf countries and that caused lack of unskilled labourers especially construction workers in Kerala the jobs which need more physical efforts. Migration is primarily happening to addressing the unemployment through a better job. Among the inter-state migrants, a small minority only getting employment in formal sector. They are compelled to work which needs more physical effort and also hazardous employment and unsafe locations.

Inter-state migration leads to the economic prosperity, development of source and destination and more number of people are getting employment. In 2013, a study conducted by Gulati Institute of Finance and Taxation, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala reveals about 30 lakhs of migrant labours are working in Kerala in different sectors. The recent report of central intelligence shows the migrants from other states in Kerala is increasing, according to the present data it is 40 lakhs. Sixty percentage of non-government jobs in the unskilled sector is done by the migrant labourers, among the 45.0 percent of labourers are from West Bengal. Annual out flow of the remittance is 25000 crores rupees (Mathrubhumi daily, dated: 30 March 2016) from Kerala to other states.

The objective of the study is to understand the migrant youth labours in the age group of 15 to 30 years are working in construction and road lying at Thiruvananthapuram district in Kerala. It examines the education pattern, nature of migration, channels of migration, asset, language known, age at migration, major attractions in Kerala.

Methodology**The Study Area**

The study conducted at Thiruvananthapuram district of Kerala state. It situated between north latitudes 8° 17' and 8° 54' and east longitudes 76° 41' and 77° 17'. The southernmost extremity, 'Parasala', is 56 kms away from Kanyakumari, the "land's end of India". The district stretches along the shores of the Arabian sea for a distance of 78 kms and the area of the district is 2192km². According to the study Domestic Migrant Labour in Kerala (2013) conducted by Gulati Institute of Finance and Taxation, Thiruvananthapuram in Kerala, the total migrant population of Thiruvananthapuram district is 4,00,000. This study used purposive sampling method and selected sample units are indicated below in the Table No.1.

Table 1 Sample Size of the Study

Bihar	Odisha	Uttar Pradesh	Jharkhand	West Bengal	Assam	Total
35	33	41	12	36	35	192

The method of study will be adopted by the researcher is both quantitative and qualitative approach and seeking information from the youth migrants of north and north-eastern states working in Kerala in the field of construction and road work.

Surveys

Employers and contractors and senior migrant labours were granted permission and supported to have an interview with migrant youth labours and collect data from them. Interview schedule used for the collection of data from the migrant labours and check list used focus group discussion (FGD) with stakeholders. The secondary sources are also collected for the study from Government records, reports, article, seminar proceedings and contractor registers. Table number 2 explains the age group of the respondents.

Data Analysis

Microsoft Excel 2016 spreadsheet package were used to enter data for sorting. Conventional content analysis was followed to code the qualitative data from the survey (Hsieh and Shannon 2005). IBM – SPSS statistics 21 used to analyse the variation in the mean value age, religion, category, marital status, education, languages known, nature of migration, attempt of migration in Kerala, information about job opportunities in Kerala, channels of migration, asset of migrant labours, attraction of Kerala for migrant labours.

Result and Discussion of the Study**Table 2 Age**

Category	Bihar Frequency (Percentage)	Odisha Frequency (Percentage)	Uttar Pradesh Frequency (Percentage)	Jharkhand Frequency (Percentage)	West Bengal Frequency (Percentage)	Assam Frequency (Percentage)
15			1 (2.4)			
17		1 (3%)				

18	1 (2.9%)	3 (9.1%)	3 (7.3%)		2 (5.6%)	2 (5.7%)
19	2 (5.7%)	3 (3%)	1 (2.4%)	1 (8.3%)	4 (11.1%)	3 (8.6%)
20	5 (14.3%)	6 (18.2%)	6 (14.6%)	2 (16.7%)	2 (5.6%)	4 (11.4%)
21	1 (2.9%)	2 (6.1%)	5 (12.2%)	3 (25%)	1 (2.8%)	7 (20%)
22	3 (8.6%)	3 (9.1%)	3 (7.3%)	2 1(6.7%)	3 (8.3%)	6 (17.1%)
23	4 (11.4%)	3 (9.1%)	3 (7.3%)		3 (8.3%)	5 (14.7%)
24	5 (14.3%)	1 (3%)	4 (9.8%)		2 (5.6%)	3 (8.6%)
25	6 (17.1%)	1 (3%)	2 (4.9%)	1 (8.3%)	1 (2.8%)	
26	1 (2.9%)	4 (12.1%)	1 (2.4%)	1 (8.3%)	4 (11.1%)	1 (2.9%)
27	1 (2.9%)	2 (6.1%)	1 (2.4%)		3 (8.3%)	1 (2.9%)
28	2 (5.7%)	3 (9.1%)	5 (12.2%)		5 (13.9%)	2 (5.7%)
29	1 (2.9%)	1 (3%)	1 (2.4%)		3 (8.3%)	
30	3 (8.6%)	2 (6.1%)	5 (12.2%)	2 (16.7%)	3 (8.3%)	

Classification of youth migrant labours based age starts at 15 and ends at 30. The migrant youth from Uttar Pradesh (UP) consists of 2.4% have an age of 15. No details of any other states in this age group. No migrant labours have an age of 16. Three percentage from Odisha, 2.9% from Assam age of 17 years. Eighteen years old migrant youth labours are seen in every state except Jharkhand. Nineteen, twenty, twenty-one and twenty-two are the common age group of migrants. Among these age group of 20 is the most common and 23, 24, 27, 28, 29 are not common among Jharkhand. Migrants above 28 age group are difficult to find out among Assamese and between 26 and 30 are not common among the migrants of Jharkhand. Thirty years is also somewhat common except Assamese.

Table 3 Religion

Religion	Bihar	Odisha	Uttar Pradesh	Jharkhand	West Bengal	Assam
Hindu	34 (97.1%)	33 (100%)	29 (70.7%)	10 (83.3%)	32 (88.9%)	30 (85.7%)
Muslim	1 (2.9%)		12 (29.3%)	2 (16.7%)	4 (11.1%)	5 (14.3%)

Here is an analysis of population based on religion. Odisha is the state having 100% migrant youth labours are belongs to Hindu religion. Next to Odisha Bihar also has very large number of hindusie. 97.1% and 2.9% of youth migrants in Bihar is under Muslim religion. In west Bengal 88.9% are hindus and 11.1 are Islams. Assam contains 85.7% of hindus and 14.3% of Muslim. In Jharkhand 83.3% youth migrant labours are hindus and 16.7% are belongs to Muslim. But UP shows the least number of hindus population (70.7) and the highest number of Muslim population (29.3%).

Table 4 Category

Category	Bihar	Odisha	Uttar Pradesh	Jharkhand	West Bengal	Assam
General					1 (2.8%)	3 (8.6%)
OBC	26 (74.3%)	25 (75.8)	35 (85.4%)	9 (75%)	17 (47.2%)	16 (45.7%)
SC/ST	7 (20%)	7 (21.2)		2 (16.7%)	16 (44.4%)	14 (40%)
Others	2 (5.7%)	1 (3%)	6 (14.6%)	1 (8.3%)	2 (5.6)	2 (5.7%)

Next is the classification of migrant youth population in different categories; general, other backward class (OBC), scheduled caste (SC/ST) and others. General category are found in Bihar, Odisha, UP, Jharkand. But in Assam 8.6% and in West Bengal 2.8% of migrant youth are under general category. OBC are commonly found in every state, their percentage is also high. 85.4% of UP migrants are from OBC, just near to it Jharkhand also own OBC population of 81.8%. but in West Bengal and Assam it is 47.2% and 45.7% respectively. No SC/ST migrants are from Uttar Pradesh. Almost half of the migrants from West Bengal and Assam are SC/ST. Three percentage of other category are found in Bihar. No other category is in Odisha.

Table 5 Marital Status

Marital Status	Bihar	Odisha	Uttar Pradesh	Jharkhand	West Bengal	Assam
Unmarried	27 (77.1%)	24 (71.7%)	31 (75.6%)	7 (58.3%)	23 (63.9%)	34 (97.1%)
Married	8 (22.9%)	9 (27.3%)	10 (24.4%)	5 (41.7%)	13 (36.1%)	1 (2.9%)

Marital status details of the migrant youth labours are given below. Largest number of people in Assam are unmarried (97.1%). Above 70% percentage of migrant youth from Bihar, Odisha and UP are also unmarried. Comparing to other states Jharkhand has least number of unmarried youth. 2.9% migrant youth labours are only recently married in Assam. But in Jharkhand, it is around 41.7%. Other states have only below 30% newly married people. The number of divorced, widowed and separated migrant youth are nil in all of the states.

Table 6 Education

Educational Status	Bihar	Odisha	Uttar Pradesh	Jharkhand	West Bengal	Assam
Never went to school	4 (11.4%)	2 (6.1%)	2 (4.9%)	1 (8.3%)	5 (13.9%)	
Knows basic reading and writing	21 (60%)	18 (54.5%)	21 (51.2%)	7 (58.3%)	8 (22.2%)	6 (17.1%)
Primary	8 (22.9%)	13 (39.4%)	11 (26.8%)	2 (16.7%)	10 (27.8%)	17 (48.6%)
Secondary			4 (9.8%)	2 (16.7%)	8 (22.2%)	9 (25.7%)
Others	2 (5.7%)		3 (7.3%)		5 (13.9%)	3 (8.6%)

Education wise analysis shows a vivid educational background of migrant youth labour (MYL). Now a day the number of people who never went to school are almost very less. In Assam it is absolutely “zero”. But in West Bengal it is 13.9% which comparatively highest. 60% of the people know to read and write in Bihar. But in Assam 17.1% only know reading and writing. Whereas people who got primary education is less. In Assam, it is 48.6% and in Jharkhand, it is very less (16.7%). No one has secondary education in Bihar and Odisha. Again, it is 16.7% in Jharkhand like primary education rate. No other migrant youth in Odisha and Jharkhand have any other educational background. But in West Bengal 13.9% MYL completed some other courses.

Table 7 Languages Known

Languages Known	Bihar	Odisha	Uttar Pradesh	Jharkhand	West Bengal	Assam
Only mother tongue	11 (31.4%)	13 (39.4%)	13 (31.7%)	2 (16.7%)	5 (13.9%)	1 (2.9%)
Hindi	1 (2.9%)	1 (3%)	2 (4.9%)	1 (8.3%)	3 (8.3%)	16 (7.1%)
Spoken knowledge of malayalam				1 (8.3%)	1 (2.8%)	
Mother tongue and Hindi	16 (45.7%)	19 (57.6%)	25 (61%)	7 (58.3%)	19 (52.8%)	25 (71.4%)
Mother tongue and Spoken knowledge of malayalam	1 (2.9%)				2 (5.6%)	
Mother tongue, Hindi and spoken knowledge of malayalam	6 (17.1%)		1 (2.4%)	1 (8.3%)	5 (13.9%)	3 (8.6%)
Others					1 (2.8%)	

Language is an important tool which is linking people together. So, it has a significant role in migration. Every migrant youth labours are well-versed in their mother tongue. So, most of them know their mother tongue and hindi too. In Assam it is a little bit high (17.1%), comparing to other states and in Bihar it is 2.9% only. The only migrant youth labours from Jharkhand and West Bengal have spoken knowledge of Malayalam, others do not have any idea about it. A great deal of migrant labours know both mother tongue and hindi.

Table 8 Nature of Migration

Nature of Migration	Bihar	Odisha	Uttar Pradesh	Jharkhand	West Bengal	Assam
Single	7 (20%)	4 (12.1%)	3 (7.3%)	1 (8.3%)	5 (13.9%)	9 (25.7%)
Group	28 (80%)	29 (87.9%)	38 (92.7%)	11 (91.7%)	31 (86.1%)	26 (74.3%)

Migration can be of single or group. From the ancient time onwards, people like group migration. Here also it is absolutely similar, 74.3% in Assam, above 80% in Bihar, Odisha and West Bengal, above 90% in Uttar Pradesh and Jharkhand are group migrant. Others prefer single migration. Only 2.8% migrant youth labours from West Bengal seek other modes of migration. Highest number of group migration is in UP. That is why the rate of their single migration is only 7.3%.

Table 9 Attempt of Migration in Kerala

Attempt of Migration	Bihar	Odisha	Uttar Pradesh	Jharkhand	West Bengal	Assam
First attempt to job in Kerala	30 (85.7%)	28 (84.8%)	37 (90.2%)	10 (83.3%)	28 (77.8%)	28 (80%)
Subsequent attempt in Kerala	5 (14.3%)	5 (15.2%)	4 (9.8%)	2 (16.7%)	8 (22.2%)	7 (20%)

For a large number of youth migration to Kerala is their first attempt in search of a job. About West Bengal, it is 77.8% and in UP it is really high (90.2%), Assam 80%.

Table 10 Information about Job Opportunities in Kerala

Information of Jobs	Bihar	Odisha	Uttar Pradesh	Jharkhand	West Bengal	Assam
Contractor	8 (22.9%)	13 (39.4%)	16 (39%)	1 (8.3%)	12 (33.3%)	14 (40%)
Friends	20 (57.1%)	13 (39.4%)	14 (34.2%)	10 (83.3%)	13 (36.1%)	15 (42.9%)
Relatives	4 (11.4%)	3 (9.1%)	11 (26.8%)	1 (8.3%)	11 (30.6%)	4 (11.4%)
Self-search	3 (8.6%)	4 (12.15%)				2 (5.7%)

Migrants are aware about job opportunities in Kerala from many sources. Contractors and friends have a major role in passing such information to them. But contractors give less information in Jharkhand, that is around 8.3%. Instead of contractors, friends take the role 83.3%. self-search is difficult for every youth migrants. That is why half of the states have no idea of self-search and a least number of migrants from other states are their limited sources for searching a job by themselves. Relatives of migrants are also having the role in informing the job details.

Table 11 Channels of Migration

Channels of Migration	Bihar	Odisha	Uttar Pradesh	Jharkhand	West Bengal	Assam
Contractor	2 (5.7%)	4 (12.1%)	10 (24.4%)	1 (8.3%)	7 (19.4%)	5 (14.3%)
Self	33 (94.3%)	29 (87.9%)	31 (75.6%)	11 (91.7%)	29 (80.6%)	30 (85.7%)

Contractor, self and agents are different channels of migration. Large number of self-migration popular among them and it is very high among people from Bihar (94.3%) and 24.4% migrants in UP depend contractors. Agents have no role in their migration.

Table 12 Asset/Own Land

Asset/own land	Bihar	Odisha	Uttar Pradesh	Jharkhand	West Bengal	Assam
Yes	23 (65.7%)	21 (63.6%)	23 (56.1%)	9 (75%)	21 (58.3%)	25 (71.4%)
No	12 (34.3%)	12 (36.4%)	18 (43.9%)	3 (25%)	15 (41.7%)	10 (28.6%)

Above 55% of migrant youth labours have own their own land in UP and West Bengal. It is above 60% in Bihar and Odisha and above 70% in Assam and Jharkhand. The remaining do not own their land. Jharkhand has 75% of own land among other states.

Table 13 Asset/Own House

Asset/Own house	Bihar	Odisha	Uttar Pradesh	Jharkhand	West Bengal	Assam
Yes	24 (68.6%)	21 (63.6%)	23 (56.1%)	9 (75%)		
No	11 (31.4%)	12 (36.4%)	18 (43.9%)			

Those migrants have own land constructed own house too. Others do not have their own house. So own land and own house are inter connected to a large extend.

Table 14 Attraction of Kerala for Migrant Labours

Types of attractions	Bihar	Odisha	Uttar Pradesh	Jharkhand	West Bengal	Assam
Attractive wages	6 (17.1%)	3 (9.1%)	5 (12.3%)	9 (74.9%)	12 (33.5%)	15 (43%)
Job	29 (82.9%)	30 (90.9%)	34 (82.9%)	3 (25.1%)	23 (63.7%)	20 (57%)
Business			2 (4.8%)			
Safe place to work					1 (2.8%)	

Many factors attract the migrant youth labours to work in Kerala. The availability of job in Kerala attracts a great many youth to flow here and work. Odisha youth (90.9%) prefer Kerala to work due to the above reason, 82.9% of migrants from UP and Bihar also consider it as reason to work. But 25.1% migrant from Jharkhand think about it. The most number of youth in Jharkhand (74.9%) are attracted by the attractive wages of Kerala. But in other states, it is not as important as Jharkhand's. Uttar Pradesh only gets an attraction of business scenario in Kerala. Only 2.8% of migrant youth labours in West Bengal feel Kerala as safer place to work. No one else feel it so.

Findings

The major purpose of the study was to understand migrant youth labours in Thiruvananthapuram district of Kerala state. The major findings of the study are follows;

- Inter-state migration starts at very young age (15years).Among the states Bihar, Odisha, Uttar Pradesh, Jharkhand, West Bengal, Assam 19, 20 age group is common age for migration.
- Hundred percentage (100%) of migrant youth labours from Odisha are Hindus. And Uttar Pradesh contributed a high percentage (29.3%) of muslim migrant labours.
- The major portion of Other Backward Class (OBC) youth came from Bihar, Odisha, UP and Jharkhand respectively 75.8%, 78.1%, 85.4% and 81.8%. Considering SC/ST migrant youth came from Bihar (21.2), Odisha (21.9), West Bengal (41.7%) and Assam (40%).
- The study shows majority of migrant youth labours are unmarried.Migrant youth from Jharkhand (8.3%) and West Bengal (2.8%) know the spoken language of Malayalam.
- Most of the respondents from every state know basic reading and writing and a large number of young people choose group migration (more than 80%) instead of individual migration.
- Except Assam a huge number (above 80%) of youth from other states are made their first attempt of migration to Kerala.
- Friends and relatives are playing a key role to provide information about the job opportunity to Kerala.
- The study shows majority (More than 80%) migrant youth find out a job in Kerala by themselves and also it reflects migrant youth labours are working here and creating assets (own land and house) (Above 60%) in their native place.
- A huge number of youth are attracted to migrate Kerala for avail an employment and attractive income.

Conclusion

Migrant youth labours are everywhere in Kerala. They are occupied in a position of unskilled and semiskilled employment in rural as well as urban area of the state. The study made an effort

to understand socio economic status of migrant youth labours under the age bracket of 15 to 30 years. Paper is showing the education pattern, age at migration, channels of migration, nature of migration, language known, major attractions of migrant youth in Kerala, asset developed by them due to their migration in Kerala. The study reflect youth especially at very young age migrant labours are flowing to Kerala. Most of them do not have good accommodation and other amenities. Still they are working hard and helping the development process at the source and destination.

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